

INFLUENCE OF WORKING ENVIRONMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN THE KENYA POLICE SERVICE

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Abstract:

Police service employees are extremely crucial to the country since their value is essentially intangible and not easily replicated. Kenya police service employees have been complaining of career growth and opportunity, better compensation, structured induction programs, performance management tools, equitable compensation packages, job satisfaction and good leadership skills were found to influence their decision to stay with their current employer. The objective of this study was to establish the influence of working environment on organizational performance in the Kenya Police Service. The study was carried out in the police services using Laikipia Police Divisional Headquarters. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The target population of the study was 86 disciplined uniformed officers who work in the Laikipia Police Division headquarters. The researcher conducted a census of all the respondents from the Laikipia Police Division headquarter. Descriptive statistics which includes frequencies and percentages were used to analyze data. The study used Pearson correlation analysis to test the hypothesis and the p-value from test statistic. The study concludes that working environment is one of the key issues in the world's Kenya police service. The study recommends that the governments should ensure that police officers are given proper working tools and equipment to improve their performance. The police department should professionally come up with a practical scheme of service

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and policies that ensures that there is no conflicting policies in the police organization structure.

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1. Introduction

In the current dynamic labour market and competitive business environment, there is need for a strategic human resource planning which enables an organization adopt various flexible patterns of employment, within the context of an organization politics in terms of recruitment, retention, motivation, and training, in order to effect an efficient movement and distribution of employees. The concept of manpower planning has become of necessity to many organizations, given the fact that organizations are becoming larger with each day, and thus planning for their labour force has become more complicated (Mungumi, 2012).

Freeman (2010) argues that there are major reasons for analyzing working environment in order to reduce the working environment. The organization must know current levels of turnover before it can decide whether steps need to be taken to reduce this rate. Objective measurement is essential if the cost of working environment is to be calculated accurately. In his study, Freeman (2010) noted that working environment will influence forecasting of the human resources in the organization and future staffing and recruitment and this needs to be estimated reliably in order to account will need to be taken of past levels of working environment.

Kenya police was legally constituted in 1906 by a police ordinance and the office of Inspector General established. The year 1926 saw the formation of the Criminal Intelligent Unit and the Railway Police Unit while in 1946 another police training depot was established. General Service Unit was later to be established in the year 1948 for rapid deployment. During the same year police training school was transferred from Nairobi, deport to Kiganjo its present site. The same year saw new Police Act brought into being. A year later in 1949 police Air wing to support communication and casualty evacuation was established. A dozen other specialized police units have since emerged.

In Kenya, police service employees are extremely crucial to the country since their value is essentially intangible and not easily replicated (Amamo, 2005). Kenya police service employees have been complaining of career growth and opportunity, better compensation, structured induction programs, performance management tools,

equitable compensation packages, job satisfaction and good leadership skills were found to influence their decision to stay with their current employer (Njoroge 2013).

2. Statement of the Problem

The Government of Kenya is committed to ensure security of all Kenyan and to protect their property and life's. To achieve this objective, His excellence the President of the Republic of Kenya, Hon. Mwai Kibaki, on 20th October 2003 passed a presidential decree declaring the government's commitment to motivate the disciplined personnel which say the Kenya police service employee's salaries increased by 300 percent (GoK, 2003). This was intended to enhance motivation to the Kenya police service personnel and increase their loyalty to the government for better services to the society. The government has been conducting recruitment of Kenya police service every year in order to increase their numbers and reduce the workload of employees. In the year 2013, the government decided to increase the mobility of disciplined personnel and hired 1,300 modern vehicles from Toyota Kenya and they were distributed across all the Kenya police service in the country. This was meant to make their work more comfortable and satisfying.

However, despite all these efforts to ensure that the disciplined personnel are satisfied and are retained within the service, the rate of employee annual turnover has increase from 12% annual in 2012 to 19% in 2015 (NPSC, 2015). The measures of recruiting 10,000 officers to balance the workforce has not been able to achieve a lot in terms of police turnover and this rate is increase every year. This is a very high rate of turn over which has remained one of the challenges the service is experiencing in the last four years (2012-2015) inclusive and this is paralyzing operations nationwide (Strategic Plan, 2013- 2018). It is from this background that an academic inquiry is needed to establish the relationship between employee turnover and organizational performance in the Kenya Police Service.

3. Research Objective

The objective of this study was to establish the influence of working environment on organizational performance in the Kenya Police Service.

3.1 Research Hypothesis

H1: There is a significant relationship between working environment and organizational performance in the Kenya Police Service.

3.2 Scope of the Study

The study was carried out in the police services using Lakipia Police Divisional Headquarters. All the police officers under the command of the police division were involved. There are 86 police officers of different ranks in the division and all of them were involved in the study.

4. Literature Review

4.1 Labor Theory

In 1964, Gary Becker coined the phrase “human capital” to refer to the idea that much of the skill and knowledge required to do a job could only be acquired if some investment was made in time and resources (Becker, 1964). Becker considered the implications of the fact that some of the knowledge and skills acquired by employees have a much higher value in a given employment relationship than they do in other potential relationships. Such specialized knowledge and skills may often be productivity enhancing, he argued, and are therefore likely to be an important part of the employment relationship in practice. But, he noted, they introduce a complication into simple models of wages, investments in training, and other terms of the employment relationship. In particular, the labor services of employees with specialized skills can no longer be modeled as undifferentiated, generic inputs, for which equilibrium price (wages) and quantity (number of employees or number of hours of work) are determined by the intersection of supply and demand curves. Once employees are understood to have specialized skills, it matters which employee does what job for what firm. Furthermore, if a firm had paid for the specific training of a worker who quit to take another job, its capital expenditure would be partly wasted, for no further return could be collected. Likewise, a worker fired after he had paid for specific training would be unable to collect any further return and would also suffer a capital loss. Where investments in specific skills are important, Becker reasoned, it is no longer a matter of indifference whether a firm’s labor force always contained the same persons or a rapidly changing group.

Although Becker’s primary interest was the economic incentives for investments in training and education, along the way he introduced a concept that provides a rationale for long-term relationships between firms and their employees. Peter Doeringer and Michael Piore built on this insight to develop their theory of internal labor markets. They argued that investments by firms in specialized training encourage firms to put in place other institutional arrangements designed to stabilize employment and reduce turnover. The organizational stability that results from these practices in

turn facilitates further development of specific skills. Doeringer and Piore further argued that the use of mass-production technology, with its detailed division of labor, requires specialized skills and makes stable employment relationships more important.

Becker also argued that employees and employers would be likely to split both the costs and returns from specialized training, to provide an incentive for both parties to stay in the relationship. This means that employees would typically earn less than their opportunity cost during the early stages of their employment relationship (while they were in training, for example), and more than their opportunity cost later in the relationship. An earnings pattern like this would produce an “upward sloping wage tenure profile, an empirical regularity that labor economists before Becker had observed, and that work by subsequent scholars has documented extensively. Consistent with the “firm-specific human capital” hypothesis, labor economists have also observed that long-tenured employees typically earn quite a bit more than their short-run opportunity cost. This empirical pattern is confirmed through employee’s working environment in the Kenya police service.

4.2 Empirical Review

Czakan (2010), much of the actual turnover in organizations has to do with the level of compensation offered by the management of satisfaction. Apart from the practical difficulty in conducting turnover research among people who have left an organization, some researchers suggest that there is a strong link between intentions to quit and actual turnover. He also noted that the relationship between intentions and turnover is consistent and generally stronger than the satisfaction-turnover relationship, although it still accounted for less than a quarter of the variability in turnover.

Organizational instability has been shown to have a high degree of high turnover. Indications are that employees are more likely to stay when there is a predictable work environment and vice versa (Zuber, 2008). In organizations where there was a high level of inefficiency, there was also a high level of staff turnover. Therefore, in situations where organizations are not stable employees tend to quit and look for stable organizations because with stable organizations they would be able to predict their career advancement. The imposition of a quantitative approach to managing the employees led to disenchantment of staff and hence it leads to working environment. Therefore, management should not use quantitative approach in managing its employees.

Simon et al. (2009) argued that all these approaches should be avoided if managers want to minimize employee turnover an increase organizational competitiveness in this environment of globalization. Employees have a strong need to

be informed. Organization with strong communication systems enjoyed lower turnover of staff. Employees feel comfortable to stay longer, in positions where they are involved in some level of the decision-making process. That is employees should fully understand about issues that affect their working atmosphere. But in the absence openness' in sharing information, employee empowerment the chances of continuity of employees are minimal.

Costly et al. (2008) points out that a high working environment may mean poor personnel policies, poor recruitment policies, poor supervisory practices, poor grievance procedures, or lack of motivation. All these factors contribute to high employee turnover in the sense that there is no proper management practices and policies on personnel matters hence employees are not recruited scientifically, promotions of employees are not based on spelled out policies, no grievance procedures in place and thus employees decides to quit. Griffeth et al. (2011) noted that pay and pay-related variables have a modest effect on turnover. Their analysis also included studies that examined the relationship between pay, a person's performance and turnover. They concluded that when high performers are insufficiently rewarded, they quit. If jobs provide adequate financial incentives, the more likely employees remain with organization and vice versa. There are also other factors which make employees to quit from organizations and these are poor hiring practices, managerial style, lack of recognition, lack of competitive compensation system in the organization and toxic workplace environment.

4.3 Conceptual Framework

5. Research Methodology

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design which is concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual, or of groups. The target population of the study was 86 disciplined uniformed officers who work in the Laikipia Police Division headquarters. These employees are of different cadres from the lowest to management level. This is because to have a clear picture, all the levels of employees needs to be involved since the turnover is cutting across all the cadres. The researcher conducted a census of all the respondents from the Laikipia Police Division

headquarter. The sample size of 86 respondents was used. The questionnaires were used to collect the data from the sample. Descriptive statistics which includes frequencies and percentages were used to analyze data. The study used Pearson correlation analysis to test the hypothesis and the p-value from test statistic was used to determine whether there is any relationship which could be attributed to the ordinary random factors or not (Berhane, 2009). Data was presented using tables and in narrative form.

5.1 Response on policies that addresses officers work life balance

The study wanted to establish from the respondents whether there are policies that address officers work life balance. Their responses were as shown in Table 1 below

Table 1: Response on policies that addresses officers work life balance

Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Agree	28	35.3	35.3	35.3
	Neutral	1	3.9	3.9	39.2
	Disagree	50	60.8	60.8	100.0
	Total	79	100.0	100.0	

Data analyzed revealed that majority of the respondents 60.8% disagreed that there policies that addresses officers work life balance. It was also found that 35.3% of the respondents agreed that there are policies that address officers work life balance while only 3.9% of the respondents were not aware of the policy. These findings agrees with a study done by Meyer and Allen (2010) who found that in order to develop the desired knowledge, skills and abilities of the employees, to perform well on the job, there is need for effective policies that addresses officers work life balance that may also influence turnover.

5.2 Response on Whether Police Officers are Provided with Good Housing Facilities

The study wanted to establish from the respondents whether police officers are provided with good housing facilities. Their responses were as shown in Table 2 below

Table 2: Whether Police officers Training is Carried Out Regularly

Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	46	58.1	58.1	58.1
	Neutral	2	4.1	4.1	62.0
	Agree	30	37.8	37.8	100.0
	Total	79	100.0	100.0	

The data indicated that majority of the respondents 58.1% disagreed that police officers are provided with good housing facilities while 37.8% agreed that police officers are provided with good housing facilities. This shows that police officers are provided with good housing facilities. These findings concur with those of Farooq & Aslam (2011) who argues that managers are trying their level best to develop the employee's capabilities through providing them with good housing facilities.

5.3 Response On Whether Management is Mindful of Officers

The study wanted to establish from the respondents whether management is mindful of officers' personal health and conditions of work hence provides comfortable tools of work for better performance. Their responses were as shown in Table 3 below

Table 3: Response On Whether Management is Mindful of Officers

	Response	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	56	70.4	70.4	70.4
	Neutral	2	3.6	3.6	74.0
	Agree	21	26.0	26.0	100.0
	Total	79	100.0	100.0	

Data revealed that majority of the respondents 70.4% disagreed that management is mindful of officers' personal health and conditions of work hence provides comfortable tools of work for better performance while 26% of the respondents agreed that management is mindful of officers' personal health and conditions of work hence provides comfortable tools of work for better performance. This shows that management is mindful of officers' personal health and conditions of work hence provides comfortable tools of work for better performance. These findings agree with a study done by Rao (2011) who found that many organizations are mindful of their employees and this gives employees confidence in their job.

5.4 Satisfaction Levels of Working Environment in the Police Services

The study wanted to establish from the level of respondents satisfaction of working environment in the police services. Their responses were as shown in Table 5 below,

Table 4: Satisfaction Levels of working environment in the police services

Response		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Highly Satisfied	6	8.5	8.5	8.5
	Satisfied	24	29.8	29.8	38.3
	Dissatisfied	45	56.4	56.4	94.7
	Highly Dissatisfied	4	5.3	5.3	100.0
	Total	79	100.0	100.0	

The data revealed that majority of the respondents 56.4% were dissatisfied with the working environment in the police services while 29.8% of the respondents were satisfied. This shows that majority of the respondents are dissatisfied with working environment in the police services. These findings differs with those of Wei-Tai (2006) who found that working environment helps in constructing a more conducive environment for the workforce and train them to cope with the upcoming challenges and employees becomes satisfied with their work.

5.5 Hypothesis Testing

Table 5: Correlations of the dependent and independent variable

Independent Variable		Working Environment
Performance (Y)	Pearson Correlation(r)	.567*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

5.6 Test of Hypothesis of Working Environment

There is a weak positive relationship between working environment and as indicated by correlation of 0.567. The p-Value of 0.002 is less than the acceptable significance level (α), hence the null hypothesis that there is no relationship between working environment and performance is rejected. This shows that the sampled data can be applied to the general population at 95% confidence level.

6. Summary, Conclusions and Recommendations

6.1 Summary

The study established that police officers are not provided with good housing facilities. It was also revealed that the cost of training is catered for by the Police department. This shows that majority of those who have been trained, the cost was catered for by the Police department. Data revealed that management is mindful of officers' personal

health and conditions of work hence provide comfortable tools of work for better performance.

6.2 Conclusions

The study concludes that working environment is one of the key issues in the world's Kenya police service. Worldwide researches have suggested that employee turnover is highest in the Kenya police service. In regard to this, no employer can ignore the issue of working environment within organizations since the costs of working environment make up the largest proportion of operation costs of businesses and organization. This makes manpower planning in an organization imperative. This is because there is great cost if highly qualified, experienced and trained employees leave. In reviewing and monitoring turnover rates and the factors influencing working environment, the management can be in a position to improve on these factors hence managing working environment.

Regardless of good planning, organizations cannot retain all their employees since in reality; staff wastage has to occur through retirement, transfers, dismissals, natural deaths and resignations. Every time an employee leaves his or her employer, there are either negative or positive consequences to the organization. In Kenya, disciplined service employees are extremely crucial to the country since their value is essentially intangible and not easily replicated. Kenya police service employees have been complaining of career growth and opportunity, better compensation, structured induction programs, performance management tools, equitable compensation packages, job satisfaction and good leadership skills were found to influence their decision to stay with their current employer.

6.3 Recommendations

The study recommends that;

- The governments should ensure that police officers are given proper working tools and equipment to improve their performance;
- The police department should professionally come up with a practical scheme of service and policies that ensures that there is no conflicting policies in the police organization structure.

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